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Development of Political Intelligence Leadership
Scale

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Abstract

In educational environments with scarce resources, school administrators must gradually improve their management skills. Not only management skills but also IQ and EQ should be developed in a related way. Although cognitive intelligence is sufficient for management, emotional intelligence is also important for understanding people. However, in a world where power is shared, it is understood that in addition to these types of intelligence, political intelligence should also exist to manage strategic interactions. For this reason, measuring the political intelligence leadership of school administrators constitutes the problem of the study. A valid and reliable political intelligence leadership scale was developed with a sample group of 597 teachers and school administrators. It is thought that the political intelligence leadership skills of school administrators can be measured through this scale. Political intelligence leadership was analyzed in four dimensions. These are futurism, trust, purposeful empathy, and power. Through political intelligence, school administrators' ability to manage strategic interactions in schools can be revealed.

Keywords:

political intelligence,
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types of leadership

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Introduction

Today, leaders work on a variety of issues to guide their organizations, institutions, or communities. The future, however, is likely to be even more complex, demanding leaders to do more than they can. The responsibilities of leaders to create a better future are becoming increasingly difficult. This is leading leaders to move forward not in isolation but collectively through strategic interactions.

In the multidimensional communication and interaction that leaders participate in, it is becoming increasingly difficult to manage the success-oriented complex structure. To overcome this situation, leaders are thought to have an intense focus and the capacity to work with many people. Leaders use their cognitive intelligence (IQ) and emotional intelligence (EQ) in most of their skills. However, to overcome intense and complex situations, it is observed that they need to have political intelligence (PQ), which is a more comprehensive type of intelligence related to IQ and EQ.

Although PQ is shaped in terms of the needs of leaders in both the business world and the state by taking leaders as the focal point in the triangle of state, business and society, the research focuses on schools in non-profit organisations, which are seen as different from the state and business world. At this point, the necessity for schools to cooperate with stakeholders to achieve their goals is interpreted as school leaders managing comprehensive cooperation through PQ.

At this point, the fact that the political intelligence leadership behaviours of school administrators are not known and there is no scale that can be used to obtain information about their political intelligence constitutes the problem of the research. Within the scope of this problem situation, the fact that the political intelligence leadership scale that will mediate the determination of political intelligence leadership behaviours of school administrators has not been developed constitutes the problem of the research. Within the scope of this problem, it is aimed to develop a valid and reliable political intelligence leadership scale for school administrators.

Theoretical Framework

Political intelligence (PQ) is a type of intelligence that enables strategic interaction in a world where power is shared to shape the future in the global economy (Reffo & Wark, 2017). The word political, which is used to reveal the type of intelligence, has a social meaning rather than political meaning. Here, the four-frame theory proposed by Bolman and Deal (2003) can also be remembered. In the Political Frame in the four-frame theory, organisations are seen

as communities living in a world of scarce resources with differences between them. In this context, it can be said that political intelligence brings richness and effectiveness to leaders who communicate and interact with various communities.

Reffo and Wark (2017), who developed the PQ leadership theory, developed it into a model and analysed it in five dimensions for individuals to develop their leadership and to develop and support other leaders or potential leaders. These dimensions are futurism, power, purposeful empathy, trust, and versatility (Reffo & Wark, 2017). Futurism is about leaders thinking about future generations and knowing how to create the conditions for a better future. Power is about building relationships and influencing stakeholders to shape the future for both profit and a better society. Empathy for purpose is about building strong and trusting relationships with stakeholders in the achievement of a common purpose and using these relationships to achieve more mutually beneficial outcomes. Trust is seen as an element that binds and enhances relationships but is also about achieving more for the common good in a network of relationships where positional power is not enough. Versatility is about having a wide range of thoughts and behaviours and the will to use them purposefully (Reffo & Wark, 2017). In this context, when political intelligence is analysed together with its sub-dimensions, it can be interpreted as preparing a better future for future generations, influencing stakeholders for this future, and using their relationships, and doing more than one is best to achieve more.

Considering that the characteristics that managers should have been managerial understanding, personal style, and political intelligence (Ciampa, 2005), the importance of political intelligence also emerges. At this point, it can be said that political ability and political intelligence are kept separate from each other. It can be expressed as the cognitive element that we use to achieve our political abilities. It can also be expressed as a cognitive process that deals with external activities from a holistic perspective.

It can be said that the use of political intelligence is quite common in organisations where political games are played. Political games can be expressed as a process that is played simultaneously in a mixed and implicit way but still has certain rules (Allison, 1969). In this context, the importance of the necessity of political intelligence in order to manage this process and to maintain communication and interaction with all stakeholders with a holistic perspective in an ever-changing environment where some rules are implicit and some are explicit and all of these rules are considered as a game can be revealed. In this context, it can be said that political intelligence is necessary for individuals in the analysis of the political arena mentioned by Bolman and Deal (2003) and in the management of this arena.

When it is considered on the basis of school, it is observed that it is a very challenging

process to approach the events with a holistic perspective by including all stakeholders (teachers, students, parents, non-governmental organisations, management organisations, etc.) in the process in the whole of various written or unwritten rules due to school culture. At this point, school administrators need to use their political intelligence to minimise the mistakes to be made by themselves and others or to reduce potential mistakes (Adams & Zanzi, 2006). At this point, it can be said that school administrators should use their political intelligence at the point of learning the characteristics of the employees, understanding the employees, and accessing the information and opportunities necessary for the school.

When both domestic and foreign studies are examined, it has been observed that studies have been carried out to develop scales related to political intelligence (Demirbağ & Yozgat, 2019), to examine political intelligence as a management concept (Ashraf & Iqbal, 2011), to examine political intelligence from various perspectives (Vélez, 2014), to examine political intelligence with various variables (Panah, Marefat, & Farahmand, 2019), but no school-specific or school-specific study has been encountered. In this context, the problem of the research is that the situation of school administrators regarding political intelligence leadership is not known.

Method

In this section, details about the methodology of the research will be given.

Research Model

The research is basic research. Basic research is a study conducted to examine, examine, strengthen, or put forward a new theory about a particular field. (Karasar, 2022). In this context, the basic research model was chosen as it was tried to develop a political intelligence scale for schools to strengthen the political intelligence theory.

Universe Sample

This research was applied to teachers and school administrators working in public schools in Denizli in the 2021-2022 academic year. 15473 teachers working in Denizli province were accepted as the population and 597 people were reached by convenient sampling method from this population. Convenient sampling is an easy-to-access and easy-to-apply method that provides convenience to the researcher. The researcher can access people close to him/her, but the bias of this method is high (Karasar, 2022). In this context, to eliminate the bias factor throughout the research, it was tried to reach more people than expected. Within the scope of the formula suggested by Cochran (1962; cited in Balcı 2013), 380 people were recommended to be included in the sample, while 597 people were reached and the bias factor was tried to be overcome. Demographic information about the sample is given in Table 1.

Table 1. Demographic information

		n	%
Gender	Male	290	48,6
	Woman	307	51,4
School Type	Pre-school	84	14,1
	Primary School	1	0,2
	Middle School	358	60
	High School	154	25,8
Education Level	Bachelor's degree	526	88,1
	Postgraduate	71	11,9
Seniority	0-4 Years	120	20,1
	5-9 Years	160	26,8
	10-14 Years	155	26
	15-19 Years	142	23,8
Mission	Administrator	170	28,5
	Teacher	427	71,5
Total		597	100

Table 1 shows that 290 (48.6%) of the participants were male and 307 (51.4%) were female. Of the participants, 84 (14.1%) were preschool teachers, 1 (0.2%) was a primary school teacher, 358 (60%) were middle school teachers, and 154 (25.8%) were high school teachers. Of the participants, 526 (88.1%) had bachelor's degree and 71 (11.9%) had postgraduate education. The seniority of the participants was categorized by the researcher and 120 (20.1%) had 0-4 years of seniority, 160 (26.8%) had 5-9 years of seniority, 155 (26%) had 10-14 years of seniority and 142 (23.8%) had 15-19 years of seniority.

Data Collection

Within the scope of the research, data were collected through Google Forms. The scale was sent to schools in Denizli province via e-mail and teachers and administrators in their schools were asked to fill it out. Afterwards, the schools with a high number of teachers were called and reminded to deliver the forms to the teachers and administrators. Data analysis was started as soon as it was thought that data saturation was reached.

Data Analysis

Within the scope of the research, before proceeding with the analysis, a check was made to remove people who did not complete the entire scale or who checked the same option in all items. After the control, it was observed that all participants were valid. Then, descriptive statistics were used to determine the normality of the distribution. After the removal of outlier data, Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) and then Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) were conducted. A certain part of the data was used for EFA and the other part for CFA, and finally

all the data were combined, and CFA was performed again.

After the factor structure of the scale was created, the factor structure was verified, and the validity and reliability tests of the scale were performed. Within the scope of validity and reliability tests, Cronbach's Alpha validity test, equivalent halves evaluate, lower-upper 27% groups test were performed. The results of the tests are given in detail in the findings section.

Findings

The analyses and validity and reliability tests conducted by adhering to the scale development stages are given in this section respectively.

Content Validity

The 60-item draft scale form created by the researchers was based on the review of the relevant literature. After the scale items were created, they were sent to two language and ten field experts for their opinions. Considering the feedback of two language and eight field experts, four items were decided to be discarded and a 56-item draft scale was created by making the necessary arrangements. To examine the comprehensibility of the scale by teachers, three teachers were interviewed, and the feedback received was sent to two language and two field experts again. Necessary arrangements were made in line with the feedback received and the last version of the draft scale was decided. The 56-item draft scale was administered to 597 participants.

Exploratory Factor Analysis

After the 56-item draft scale with content validity was applied to 597 participants, the data obtained were subjected to exploratory factor analysis. In the exploratory factor analysis, the normality of the distribution was first evaluated, and the Mahalanobis Distance Coefficient was examined. The extreme values obtained because of the Mahalanobis Distance Coefficient were discarded and the mode, median, arithmetic mean, kurtosis, and skewness values of the remaining data were examined. To obtain a distribution close to a normal distribution, it is recommended that the mode, median, arithmetic mean values should be close to each other, and the kurtosis and skewness values should be between -1 and +1. Descriptive statistics of the distribution are given in Table 2.

Table 2. Descriptive statistics of the data group

Descriptive Statistics

Mod	170
Median	171
Arithmetic Mean	173,01
Kurtosis	-0,34
Standard Error of Kurtosis	,100
Skewness	0,555
Skewness Standard Error	0,200

When Table 2 is examined, it is observed that the mode, median and arithmetic mean values are close to each other, and the kurtosis and skewness values are between -1 and +1. In this case, it can be accepted that the distribution shows a normal distribution.

A total of 76 data were discarded to eliminate outliers and to ensure a distribution close to the normal distribution, and 521 data were left for analysis out of 597 data. It was decided to use the first 350 data for EFA and the remaining 171 data for CFA. For a second CFA, it was deemed appropriate to combine all the data and repeat with a data set of 521 people.

For exploratory factor analysis, the Kaiser-Meyer Olkin (KMO) coefficient, which compares the magnitude of the observed correlation coefficients with the magnitude of the partial correlation coefficients, was first examined. It is recommended that this value should be close to 1 and Bartlett's test of sphericity should be significant. (Çokluk, Şekercioğlu, & Büyüköztürk, 2018). KMO and Bartlett's Sphericity Test results of the data are given in Table 3.

Table 3. Political Intelligence Leadership Scale Statistics

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Suitability	,735	
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Chi-Square Value	46017,514
	Sd	1540
	p	,000

When Table 3 is examined, it is observed that the KMO value is appropriate for factor analysis. The fact that the KMO value is greater than .50 indicates that the factoring process can be started, and the fact that Bartlett's Sphericity Test is significant indicates that the data come from a multivariate normal distribution. (Çokluk, Şekercioğlu, & Büyüköztürk, 2018). It is observed that Bartlett's Test of Sphericity is significant [$\chi^2(1540) = 46017,514; p < .01$].

To determine the number of factors and the percentage of the total variance explained in the data suitable for factor analysis, factor analysis procedures were started. The number of factors and total variances explained are given in Table 4.

Table 4. PQL Scale Variances Table

Initial Core Values	Factor Loadings Sum of Squares
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Factor	Initial Eigenvalues		Sum of Factor Loads Squares			
	Total	Variance Explained (%)	Total Variance Explained (%)	Total	Variance Explained (%)	Total Variance Explained (%)
1	8,834	15,774	15,774	8,834	15,774	15,774
2	7,891	14,091	29,866	7,891	14,091	29,866
3	4,375	7,812	37,678	4,375	7,812	37,678
4	4,035	7,206	44,884	4,035	7,206	44,884
5	2,674	4,775	49,659	2,674	4,775	49,659
6	1,685	3,009	52,668	1,685	3,009	52,668
7	1,163	2,078	54,746	1,163	2,078	54,746
8	1,036	1,850	56,596	1,036	1,850	56,596

When Table 4 is examined, it is observed that there are 8 factors with eigenvalues above 1 and the total variance explained by these factors is 56%. It is seen that there are two factors with an explained variance above 5% and an eigenvalue above 1. However, four factors are considered to make a significant contribution by the researchers. Factor analysis was continued to determine the factors and the items under the factors.

To maximize the factor loading values, Varimax rotation technique was used to group the items under the most appropriate factors. Varimax rotation brings the loading values of the items closer to 1 or 0 so that the factor variances are maximized. (Çokluk, Şekercioğlu, & Büyüköztürk, 2018). As a result of the rotation, it was observed that the items were grouped under four factors and the number of items in the other factors was insufficient.

The factor loading value can be determined by the researcher during rotation. The researchers decided that the factor loading value should be .45. A factor loading value of .45 indicates that the variance explained by the item is 20% and that it moderately measures the feature it wants to measure. (Çokluk, Şekercioğlu, & Büyüköztürk, 2018). The items with factor loadings below .45 or showing overlap in the factors were removed from the draft scale one by one and EFA was repeated each time and the aggregation of the items under the factors was examined. After the removal of 20 items, it was observed that the remaining 36 items were grouped under 4 factors and the total variance explained was 46.099%.

Before examining the factors in which the items were collected, the correlation between the items and the total score was examined and the correlation between the item total score and the items was examined and it was examined whether there was a multicollinearity problem. It is accepted that items with an item total score correlation below .30 do not

measure the same construct. (Çokluk, Şekercioğlu, & Büyüköztürk, 2018). As a result of the examination, it was observed that there was no multicollinearity problem. The factor loadings of the 36 items and 4-factor structure formed because of the exploratory factor analysis are given in Table 5.

Table 5. PQL Item Statistics

Factor	Article	Expression	Factor Load Value
1	M32	It enables people around it to unite around common values	,834
	M2	Generates ideas on solving the future needs of future generations.	,834
	M35	Supports projects that will benefit society	,830
	M5	He thinks that it is necessary to have knowledge to establish a connection between the past and the future.	,828
	M33	Makes school priorities clear to teachers	,816
	M3	Predicts situations that will affect society in the future	,811
	M4	It has suggestions on how the developments in the world will be reflected in education.	,807
	M1	Thinking for future generations to have a better future	,784
	M6	Takes care to take the ideas of school stakeholders for the future	,769
	M36	Manages conflicts of interest in the school without harming the trust of the parties	,767
	2	M9	Balances different ideas about the future of the school
M39		Ensures that all work in the school is transparent	,850
M7		Develop joint strategies for the future with neighboring schools	,818
M37		Supports taking bold steps to solve problems	,811
M8		Strives to create the conditions for a productive outcome with the surrounding schools	,793
M38		Ensures that the step they take is in accordance with ethical principles	,790
M12		Influence's school stakeholders in line with the objectives by using his/her charisma	,632
3	M42	Rely on the support of colleagues	,627
	M17	Evaluates problems logically	,801
	M47	Considers the results of previous studies to act in accordance with environmental conditions	,797
	M46	Has the ability to quickly initiate collaborative efforts with the school's stakeholders	,749
	M16	Courageous in taking rational risks	,747
	M19	Transfer the experiences gained with colleagues in different countries to their own environment (school, system, etc.)	,715
	M49	Attempts to resolve ambiguity in situations of uncertainty	,715
	M48	Takes human emotions into account in various school-related issues	,651

	M18	Has foresight about environmental developments that may be related to education	,647
	M21	Uses different forms of communication (stories, anecdotes, metaphors, aphorisms, etc.) to better explain complex situations	,639
4	M51	Objectively sets out the aims of their work	,637
	M23	Uses legal powers where necessary to deal with complex situations	,842
	M53	His lack of effort to prove what he is sure of makes him impressive	,841
	M52	Knows the importance of reassuring managerial behaviors in achieving the purpose of the school	,793
	M22	Uses expertise to assist school stakeholders in situations of uncertainty	,792
	M25	Seeks to understand the characteristics of stakeholders to better grasp their expectations	,751
	M55	Does not make decisions without understanding the consequences of ongoing processes	,750
	M28	Believes that it is important to understand the values held by the people around them	,662
	M27	Takes time to get to know the people they will collaborate with	,604

When Table 5 is examined, it is observed that a 4-factor structure was formed, and item loadings ranged between .604 and .854. If we need to name the factors, we can use the name "Futurism" for factor 1, "Trust" for factor 2, "Purposeful Empathy" for factor 3, and "Power" for factor 4. These names were chosen by Reffo and Wark (2017) because they are appropriate for the dimensioning of political intelligence. After determining the factor structures and the items collected under the factors, the confirmatory factor analysis phase was started to evaluate the verifiability of the created structure.

Confirmatory Factor Analysis

Confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) evaluates the statistical significance of the model revealed by exploratory factor analysis, that is, the degree to which the sample data validate the model. (Çokluk, Şekercioğlu, & Büyüköztürk, 2018). Since the first 350 of the 521 data constituting the sample group were used for EFA, CFA was conducted with the remaining 171 data, and then all data were combined and repeated with a total of 521 data.

For CFA, the t value is first checked, and a t value higher than 1.96 is significant at the .05 level, and a t value higher than 2.56 is significant at the .01 level. (Şimşek, 2007). When the t value was examined in the study, it was observed that it was greater than 2.56 and significant at the level of .01. The model obtained because of EFA was prepared for CFA and the model was evaluated. The tested model is given in Figure 1.

Figure 1. CFA Model

When Figure 1 is examined, it is observed that the model is validated with standardized regression loadings. The goodness of fit indices of the model were examined with both 521 and 171 data. Goodness of fit indices and references about the status of the indices are given in Table 6.

Table 6. CFA Fit Indices

Goodness of Fit Tests	Measurement Model (171 data)	Measurement Model (521 data)	Criteria	Compliance Status	References
X^2	560,93	506,369	-	-	-
sd	313	302	-	-	-
X^2 / sd	1,792	1,677	$X^2 / sd \leq 2$	Perfect Fit	Sumer (2000)
RMSEA	,039	,042	$RMSEA \leq 0.05$	Perfect Fit	(Çokluk, Şekercioğlu, & Büyüköztürk, 2018)
CFI	,918	,923	≥ 0.90	Normal value	Sumer (2000)
NFI	,906	,917	≥ 0.90	Normal value	(Çokluk, Şekercioğlu, & Büyüköztürk, 2018)

When Table 6 is examined, it is observed that the fit indices are within the perfect fit or normal value ranges. It can be said that the structural validity of the model was ensured with CFA conducted with both 171 data and 521 data. After the construct validity was established, other validity and reliability analyses were initiated.

Reliability Analyses

Three analyses were conducted to evaluate the reliability of the Political Intelligence Scale. These are Cronbach's Alpha test; equivalent halves evaluate and lower upper 27% groups test. After the Cronbach's Alpha results were analyzed, the scale items were divided into two groups as odd-numbered and even-numbered, and the equivalent halves test was performed. Then, it was examined whether there was a significant difference between the upper 27% group and the lower 27% group according to the total score. The analysis results of the tests performed are given in Table 7.

Table 7. Reliability analysis results

	Test	Futurism Dimension	Trust Dimension	Purposeful Empathy Dimension	Power Dimension	Political Intelligence Scale
	Cronbach's Alpha	,837	,833	,832	826	,919
Equivalent Halves Test	1st half	,880	,813	,797	,799	,765
	2nd half	,783	,759	,768	,791	,804
	Spearman-Brown Coefficient	,728	,746	,752	,739	,799
Lower upper 27% groups test	t	-18,937	-15,712	-19,081		-50,822
	p	<,001	<,001	<,001		<,001

When Table 7 is examined, it is observed that the reliability coefficient of the Cronbach's Alpha test is .919 and this value shows that both the sub-dimensions and the scale are dependable. It is recommended that the Cronbach's Alpha result should be above .70 (Çokluk, Şekercioğlu, & Büyüköztürk, 2018). When the scale, which has 36 items in total, was divided into two groups of 18 items as odd-numbered items and even-numbered items and the equivalent halves test was performed, it was observed that a proficient level of reliability was achieved between these two groups equidistantly. The Spearman-Brown coefficient shows that the scale is dependable. When it was examined whether there was a significant difference between the lower 27% group and the upper 27% group according to the total score, it was observed that there was a significant difference ($p < .01$) between the total

scores. These studies show that the scale is dependable.

Discussion

Within the scope of the findings, a valid and reliable Political Intelligence Leadership Scale (PQLS) was developed. When the studies conducted were examined, it was observed that political intelligence studies (Ashraf & Iqbal, 2011; Demirbağ & Yozgat, 2019; Panah et al., 2019; Vélez, 2014) were considered through the business world. The reason for the absence of these studies in the field of education may be that educational studies are not seen as strategic. In addition, since the school is in a structure that is affected by the society (Balci, 2011), it may be thought to be in a structure that adapts to the situation because it is affected by its environment. However, it is thought that the school should be in a structure that affects the society and directs the future. For this reason, strategic thinking in managing scarce resources as stated by Bolman & Deal (2003) in the Political Arena and the skills of influencing stakeholders and shaping the future as stated by Reffo & Wark (2017) should be in school administrators.

When the developed PQLS is analysed, it is seen that it has four dimensions, and these dimensions are compatible with the theory of political intelligence. However, the theory of political intelligence is presented in five dimensions. "Versatility" dimension was not included in the developed scale. This situation can be explained in two diverse ways. Participants think that school administrators should already have versatile thinking skills. Or the participants do not believe that school administrators should think in a multidimensional way due to central administration. They may believe it is not very important for school administrators to have multidimensional thinking skills because the central administration deals with and implements a subject by considering it in every dimension. However, when the literature is examined, it is stated that the decision-making process, which is the basis of school management, is actually a multidimensional thinking process, and the opinions of the people who will be affected by the decision and informal groups should be taken (Kıranlı & İlğan, 2007). In this case, the probability of the second opinion decreases. It is thought that the participants are more likely to think that a school administrator should already have multidimensional thinking skills. In the future, this situation can be revealed with a different study.

Conclusion and Recommendations

In this study, which was prepared for the development of the Political Intelligence

Leadership Scale, firstly, the content validity was tried to be ensured by creating an item pool. Afterwards, a pilot study was conducted to understand the equivalence of the scale in the field and necessary arrangements were made. After the content validity was ensured, exploratory and confirmatory factor analyses were performed, and construct validity was evaluated. After the construct validity was established, reliability analyses were performed, and a reliable scale was obtained. These studies show that a valid and reliable Political Intelligence Leadership Scale was obtained.

Considering the developed PQLS and its sub-dimensions, if it is necessary to define political intelligence leadership, it can be said that "it is the type of leader who works for the continuation of the existence of the school and future generations in better conditions, influences the environment for this purpose and establishes strong relationship networks with the environment". However, as a shorter definition, it can be said "It is the type of leader who influences the environment for future generations and manages relationship networks to achieve more". Based on this definition, it can be said that the key words of political intelligence leadership are future generations, relationship networks and common interests.

With this scale, it will be tried to measure the political intelligence in the leadership styles of the administrators in schools or whether they use political intelligence leadership during management. However, it is an important limitation that the study was conducted in Denizli province. In addition, the low proportion of primary school teachers in the sample is another limitation. In this context, it is recommended that the study should be conducted again in different provinces and primary school level and the construct validity should be verified again.

References

- Adams, S. M., & Zanzi, A. (2006). Developing political intelligence for making feasible decisions. *Journal of Management Development*, 25(4), s. 350-367.
- Allison, G. T. (1969). Conceptual Models and the Cuban Missile Crisis. *The American Political Science Review*, 63(3), s. 689-718.
- Ashraf, F., & Iqbal, M. Z. (2011). A research agenda on the leaders' political intelligence for effective change management. *African Journal of Business Management*, 5(14), s. 5798-5806. doi:10.5897/AJBM11.189
- Balcı, A. (2013). *Sosyal Bilimlerde Araştırma*. Ankara: Pegem Akademi.
- Bolman, L. G., & Deal, T. E. (2003). *Reframing organizations: Artistry, choice, and leadership*. San Francisco, CA, United States: Jossey-Bass.
- Ciampa, D. (2005). Almost ready: How leaders move. *Harvard Business Review Special Issue*, 83(1), s. 46-53.

- Çokluk, Ö., Şekercioğlu, G., & Büyüköztürk, Ş. (2018). Sosyal Bilimler İçin Çok Değişkenli İstatistik: SPSS ve LISREL Uygulamaları. Ankara: Pegem Akademi.
- Demirbağ, O., & Yozgat, U. (2019). POLİTİK HAYVAN'IN BİLİŞSEL DÖNÜŞÜMÜ: POLİTİK ZEKÂYA YÖNELİK BİR DEĞERLENDİRME. Beykoz Akademi Dergisi, 7(2), s. 147-182. doi: 10.14514/BYK.m.26515393.2019.7/2
- Karasar, N. (2022). Bilimsel Araştırma Yöntemleri (37. Baskı b.). Ankara: Nobel Yayıncılık.
- Panah, E. Y., Marefat, D., & Farahmand, F. (2019). The Relationship between Political Intelligence and Verbal Intelligence with Developmental Leadership Style of Managers and Employees of the Ministry of Youth and Sports. Organizational Behavior Management in Sport Studies, 5(20), s. 101-108.
- Reffo, G., & Wark, V. (2017). Liderlik ve Politik Zeka (2. Baskı b.). İstanbul: Türkiye İş Bankası Kültür Yayınları.
- Sümer, N. (2000). Yapısal Eşitlik Modelleri: Temel Kavramlar ve Örnek Uygulamalar. Türk Psikoloji Yazıları, 3(6), s. 49-73.
- Şimşek, Ö. F. (2007). Yapısal Eşitlik Modellemesine Giriş, Temel İlkeler ve LISREL Uygulamaları. Ankara: Ekinoks Eğitim ve Danışmanlık Hizmetleri, Siyasal Basın ve Dağıtım.
- Vélez, F. R. (2014). Political Intelligence and National Security in Ecuador: A Retrospective Reading. Journal of Power, Politics & Governance, 2(3&4), s. 115-13636.

Appendix 1

POLITICAL INTELLIGENCE SCALE		Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Undecided	I agree.	Completely Agree
1	It enables people around it to unite around common values					
2	Generates ideas on solving the future needs of future generations.					
3	Supports projects that will benefit society					
4	He thinks that it is necessary to have knowledge to establish a connection between the past and the future.					
5	Makes school priorities clear to teachers					
6	Predicts situations that will affect society in the future					
7	It has suggestions on how the developments in the world will be reflected in education.					
8	Thinking for future generations to have a better future					
9	Takes care to take the ideas of school stakeholders for the future					
10	Manages conflicts of interest in the school without harming the trust of the parties					
11	Balances different ideas about the future of the school					
12	Ensures that all work in the school is transparent					
13	Develop joint strategies for the future with neighboring schools					
14	Supports taking bold steps to solve problems					
15	Strives to create the conditions for a productive outcome with the surrounding schools					

- 16 Ensures that the step they take is in accordance with ethical principles
- 17 Using his/her charisma, he/she influences school stakeholders in line with the objectives
- 18 Rely on the support of colleagues
- 19 Evaluates problems logically
- 20 Considers the results of previous studies to act in accordance with environmental conditions
- 21 Has the ability to quickly initiate collaborative efforts with the school's stakeholders
- 22 Courageous in taking rational risks
- 23 Transfer the experiences gained with colleagues in different countries to their own environment (school, system, etc.)
- 24 Attempts to resolve ambiguity in situations of uncertainty
- 25 Takes human emotions into account in various school-related issues
- 26 Has foresight about environmental developments that may be related to education
- 27 Uses different forms of communication (stories, anecdotes, metaphors, aphorisms, etc.) to better explain complex situations
- 28 Objectively sets out the aims of their work
- 29 Uses legal powers where necessary to deal with complex situations
- 30 His lack of effort to prove what he is sure of makes him impressive
- 31 Knows the importance of reassuring managerial behaviors in achieving the purpose of the school
- 32 Uses expertise to assist school stakeholders in situations of uncertainty
- 33 Seeks to understand the characteristics of stakeholders to better grasp their expectations
- 34 Does not make decisions without understanding the consequences of ongoing processes
- 35 Believes that it is important to understand the values of the people around them
- 36 Takes time to get to know the people they will collaborate with

Appendix 2

POLİTİK ZEKA ÖLÇEĞİ		Hiç Katılmıyorum	Katılmıyorum	Kararsızım	Katılıyorum	Tamamen Katılıyorum
1	Çevresindeki kişilerin ortak değerler etrafında birleşmesini sağlar					
2	Gelecek kuşakların gelecekteki ihtiyaçlarının çözümü üzerinde fikirler üretir.					
3	Toplumsal yarar sağlayacak projelere destek verir					
4	Geçmiş ile gelecek arasında bağ kurabilmek için bilgi sahibi olmanın gerekli olduğunu düşünür					
5	Okulun önceliklerini öğretmenlere açık hale getirir					
6	Gelecekte toplumu etkileyecek olası durumları tahmin eder					

- 7 Dünyadaki gelişmelerin eğitime nasıl yansıtacağı konusunda önerilere sahiptir.
 - 8 Gelecek kuşakların daha iyi bir geleceğe sahip olması için düşünür
 - 9 Okul paydaşlarının geleceğe yönelik fikirlerini almaya özen gösterir
 - 10 Okuldaki çıkar çatışmalarını tarafların güven duygularına zarar vermeden yönetir
 - 11 Okulun geleceğine yönelik farklı düşünceleri dengeler
 - 12 Okuldaki tüm çalışmaların şeffaf olmasına özen gösterir
 - 13 Çevredeki okullar ile geleceğe yönelik ortak stratejiler geliştirir
 - 14 Sorunların çözümünde cesur adımlar atılmasını destekler
 - 15 Çevredeki okullar ile üretken bir sonuç için gereken şartları yaratmaya çaba gösterir
 - 16 Attığı adımın etik ilkelere uygun olmasına dikkat eder
 - 17 Karizmasını kullanarak okul paydaşlarını amaçlar doğrultusunda etkiler
 - 18 Çalışma arkadaşlarının desteğine güvenir
 - 19 Sorunları mantıklı bir şekilde değerlendirir
 - 20 Çevresel şartlara uygun olarak hareket etmek amacıyla önceki çalışmaların sonuçlarını dikkate alır
 - 21 Okulun paydaşları ile hızlıca ortak çalışmalar başlatma yeteneği vardır
 - 22 Akılcı riskler alma konusunda cesurdur
 - 23 Farklı ülkelerdeki meslektaşları ile edindiği deneyimleri kendi ortamına (okul, sistem vs.) aktarır
 - 24 Belirsizlik durumlarında belirsizliği gidermeye çalışır
 - 25 Okula ilişkin çeşitli konularda insani duyguları dikkate alır
 - 26 Eğitim ile ilgili olabilecek çevresel gelişmeler hakkında öngörü sahibidir
 - 27 Karmaşık durumların daha iyi anlatabilmek için farklı (hikayeler, fıkralar, metaforlar, özlü sözler vs.) iletişim biçimleri kullanır
 - 28 Çalışmalarının amaçlarını nesnel bir şekilde ortaya koyar
 - 29 Karmaşık durumların üstesinden gelmek için gerekli durumlarda yasal güçlerini kullanır
 - 30 Emin olduğu konularda ispat çabasına girmemesi onun etkileyici kılar
 - 31 Okulun amacına ulaşmasında güven verici yönetici davranışların önemini bilir
 - 32 Belirsizlik durumlarında okul paydaşlarına yardımcı olabilmek için uzmanlığını kullanır
 - 33 Paydaşların beklentilerini daha iyi kavramak için onların özelliklerini anlamaya çalışır
 - 34 Devam eden süreçlerin sonuçlarını anlamadan karar vermez
 - 35 Çevresindeki kişilerin sahip oldukları değerleri anlamanın önemli olduğuna inanır
 - 36 Ortak çalışmalar yapacağı kişileri tanımak için zaman ayırır
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